

Catalytic Vapour Phase Oxidation of Organic Compounds in the Fixed as well as in Fluidized Beds

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Oxidation plays an important role in the organic chemical industry. The controlled catalytic oxidation of hydrocarbons or other organic compounds to obtain commercially important intermediate oxidation products, is the most promising field and has great utility in petro-chemical as well as coal-chemical industries. Among the more important chemicals, which are products of oxidation, may be mentioned phthalic anhydride, ethylene oxide, adipic acid, acrolein, and various other oxygenated organic compounds.

Since there is generally a scope for improvements in conversions and reduction in cost, research and development efforts are being constantly pursued in this segment of the chemical process industry. With this in view, the catalytic oxidation of ethylene, benzene, crotonaldehyde and *o*-, *m*- and *p*-xylenes, etc. was exhaustively studied by Bhattacharyya and his coworkers. The results obtained in their earlier investigations have already been reported.

In the present article, the important contributions made by Bhattacharyya and his school in this field during the last few years have been briefly reviewed and the results of their recent and unpublished work, specially those in the fluidized bed operations, have been incorporated. The work of other eminent researchers have also been referred to in course of the discussion.

Oxidation of Ethylene to Ethylene Oxide

The catalytic oxidation of ethylene to ethylene oxide, employing a static bed of catalyst, has been the subject of a number of patents and a few papers. The catalyst generally employed consists of silver oxide deposited on metallic or non-metallic supports. The only earlier and significant published work on the oxidation of ethylene seems to be that of McBee *et al.*¹ who employed synthetic corundum as the carrier. A conversion of 30% (on the basis of ethylene fed) and a selectivity of 45% for ethylene oxide were reported at a space velocity of 1,500 with an air-ethylene ratio of 17.5

Bhattacharyya and his coworkers made a systematic and exhaustive study on this reaction in a flow reactor using fixed catalyst beds employing a large number of catalyst compositions. For experimental procedure and elaborate discussion reference may be made of previous publications of Bhattacharyya *et al.*²

The catalytic oxidation of ethylene was systematically investigated from manifold aspects, viz., the suitability of different oxidising catalysts, effect of catalyst supports, promoter action of different elements, etc. Preliminary studies indicated that the oxida-

tion proceeded specifically on the silver oxide catalyst; the other catalysts used were either inactive or led to complete oxidation to carbon dioxide and water. With a view to securing high conversions to ethylene oxide, the effect of a number of substances as promoters for silver oxide catalyst was studied. These studies indicated that such substances might be broadly classified as follows:

(i) Substances indifferent in nature, bringing about little or no change in activity of silver oxide, e.g., oxides of tin and zinc.

(ii) Substances which lead to an enhancement in activity of silver oxide catalyst without causing a marked fall in selectivity, e.g., compounds containing lithium, copper, calcium, strontium, barium, and magnesium.

(iii) Substances extremely degradative in nature, e.g., oxides of mercury, iron or manganese.

(iv) Substances causing partial or total loss in activity of silver oxide, e.g., compounds containing sodium, potassium, lead, or chlorides.

As a catalyst support, quartz was found superior to pumice, kieselguhr, activated alumina, alumina gel, silica gel, etc. The activity of the catalyst was partially lost on incorporation of sodium, while potassium completely poisoned the catalyst. The promoter action of the alkaline earth elements was in the order: $Mg > Ba > Ca > Sr$. The activity of the silver oxide-quartz catalyst was considerably enhanced by the addition of small amounts of barium peroxide. The fresh catalyst thus obtained gave a conversion of 39.7% ethylene to ethylene oxide with a selectivity of 62.6% at 290°, space velocity of 1500 c.c./hr.c.c. and air/ethylene ratio of 9. The value was as high as 38.6% conversion and 63.8% selectivity after a use of 70 hours. A higher activity was shown by a catalyst promoted by magnesium oxide. Conversion of about 43% with a selectivity of 64% was obtained per single pass at 280° with the same space velocity and air/ethylene ratio as above. The activity of the magnesium oxide promoted catalyst was, however, found to decrease after a use of 70 hours and the reaction temperature thereafter had to be increased to secure the same conversion as the fresh catalyst. The effect of temperature on the activity of the best catalyst, that is, Ag_2O - BaO_2 -quartz (31.39:1.84:100) is shown in Fig. 1.

In order to elucidate the mode of action of various catalysts, decomposition of ethylene oxide was studied on some representative catalysts and supports at various temperatures. These studies indicated that the 'degradative' action of iron, manganese, etc. was due to their promotion of instability of ethylene oxide.

With a view to ascertaining the optimum conditions for obtaining maximum yield of ethylene oxide from ethylene in presence of silver-based catalysts, the effects of a number of reaction variables, viz., catalyst concentration, method of preparation of catalyst, time of contact, etc., were studied. These studies indicated that a concentration of 32.39 g. of silver oxide on 100 g. of purified quartz was the optimum for oxidation reaction. The effect of a number of promoters indicated that barium oxide and magnesium oxide were efficient promoters for the silver oxide catalysts.

The presence of water vapour in concentrations beyond 0.4% (by volume) in the inlet gas lowered the efficiency of the oxidation. The fall in activity was independent of the concentration of the water vapour for values between 1 and 5% of the inlet gas. It was found that the catalyst, which had undergone partial inactivation on prolonged use, was completely restored to the state of its original activity by treatment with a gas mixture containing ethylene, air, and small amounts of water vapour,

FIG. 1. Effect of temperature on the activity of silver oxide-barium oxide-quartz catalyst.

S.V. $\approx$ 1530

Air/C₂H₄ $\approx$ 32

Fresh Catalyst

Used Catalyst

Conversion to C₂H₄O

Conversion to CO₂

× : S.T.Y. Δ : Selectivity.

Marked loss in the efficiency of the oxidation was found to result when ethylene, prepared from ethanol was used without any elaborate purification to remove impurities like butadiene, carbon dioxide, and possibly small amounts of ether. The time of contact of the gas with the catalyst (space velocity) had a pronounced effect on the efficiency of the oxidation. While the conversions to ethylene oxide and carbon dioxide decreased with increasing space velocity, the space-time-yield of ethylene oxide registered a progressive rise under these conditions. The efficiency of the oxidation also depended on the concentration of ethylene in the gas mixture; with decreasing concentrations, the space-time-yield of ethylene oxide progressively decreased.

The activity of the catalyst also depended on its method of preparation. The catalyst, prepared by coprecipitating barium and silver carbonates from a mixture of barium and silver nitrate solutions and subsequently reducing the carbonate mixture, was found to be less active than the catalyst, prepared by mixing silver oxide with barium peroxide mechanically. The barium oxide-promoted catalyst, prepared by using silver oxide precipitated at 60°, had higher optimum activity than the catalysts containing silver oxide precipitated at 0° or 100°.

Very recently Twigg³ has studied the kinetics of this reaction in a flow reactor using a silver catalyst. The mechanism suggested by him and supported by Murray⁴ involves the chemisorption of oxygen atoms on the catalyst surface followed by the reaction of gaseous or weakly adsorbed ethylene molecules either with one oxygen atom to form ethylene oxide or with two atoms to form products (like CH₃CHO) that are rapidly oxidised to CO₂. Murray later found that the oxidation of ethylene to ethylene oxide involved an activation energy of 12 K cal., whereas the corresponding reaction to CO₂ had an activation energy of 15 K cal.

Recently Andrianova and Todes⁵ have put forward the following kinetic equation for the range of conditions investigated by them.

$$\frac{-d(C_2H_4)}{dt} = 100 e^{\frac{13,000}{RT}} \times (u)^{\frac{1}{2}} [O_2]^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

where u = volumetric gas flow rate.

Orzechowski and MacCormack⁶ from their elaborate studies on the kinetics of ethylene oxidation with Ag-catalyst have suggested the following scheme:

Where y is isomeric with ethylene oxide (i.e. CH_3CHO , $CH_2=CHOH$ etc.) and is very rapidly oxidised to CO_2 and H_2O .

It has recently been reported that in some factories the oxidation of ethylene to ethylene oxide is also carried out in the fluidized catalyst bed, but all their findings are carefully guarded by patents.

The present authors have undertaken this problem of oxidation of ethylene to ethylene oxide in the fluidized catalyst bed and the work is in progress.

Oxidation of Benzene to Maleic Acid

Maleic acid, in view of its highly reactive nature and of the reactivity of its anhydride and amide, finds numerous applications in chemical industry. Of the many hydrocarbons, open chained or ringed, benzene seems to be the most profitable choice as the starting material for maleic acid.

A considerable amount of work has been done on the vapour phase catalytic oxidation of benzene. Special mention may be made of the contributions due to Weiss and Downs⁷. But the results of most of these investigations are covered by patents and very little is disclosed concerning the method of approach to the problem, the nature of the catalysts employed, and the details of experimental conditions or the results obtained.

A survey of the published work on the oxidation of benzene in the vapour phase shows that the maximum conversion by maleic acid is about 57% on the weight of benzene used, per single pass. The catalyst employed was $V_2O_5 - MoO_3$ (70:30)-pumice, promoted with 5% Co_2O_3 . But much higher conversions are disclosed in the patent literature. It was therefore considered worthwhile to try to raise the efficiency of the process by judicious selection of catalysts.

Bhattacharyya and Venkataraman⁸ studied the oxidation of benzene with a large number of catalyst compositions (single, binary, promoted, unpromoted, supported, and unsupported) under a wide range of operating conditions. Their observations have already been reported. The salient points of their findings will be discussed here.

Previous studies on the oxidation of benzene to maleic acid have been carried out mainly with catalysts supported on substances like pumice, asbestos, or metallic aluminium. Preliminary experiments showed, however, that kieselguhr was the most promising catalyst support.

A systematic study was therefore undertaken and forty different catalyst compositions were tried, of which the following catalyst systems were found to be quite active:

- (1) V_2O_5 — kieselguhr (51.84:100)
- (2) MoO_3 — kieselguhr (48.72:100)
- (3) WO_3 — kieselguhr (50.17:100)
- (4) $V_2O_5 : MoO_3 : kieselguhr$ (38.9 : 16.64:100)
- (5) $V_2O_5 : WO_3 : kieselguhr$ (38.9 : 4.32 : 100)
- (6) $V_2O_5 : WO_3 : kieselguhr$ (38.9 : 16.64 : 100)
- (7) $V_2O_5 : UO_3 : kieselguhr$ (38.9 : 4.32 : 100)
- (8) $V_2O_5 : UO_3 : kieselguhr$ (38.9 : 16.64 : 100)

The comparative activity of the above single and binary catalyst systems are summarised here.

Catalyst (1) was found to be more efficient than the pumice or asbestos-supported catalysts described by earlier workers. More than 27% conversion to maleic acid was possible with this catalyst in a contact time of 0.2 sec.

Catalysts (2) and (3) had poor activity. Catalyst (4) was very active and had the additional advantage of being fairly efficient over a wide range of space velocity. Thus, the conversion to maleic acid was 57% at 2618 l./h./l., and 51% at 11000 l./h./l. Consequently, maximum S. T. Y. was considerably higher than in the case of catalyst (1). Catalysts (5-8) were more active under some experimental conditions than catalyst (1), but were less active than catalyst (4).

Kieselguhr, pumice, asbestos, silica gel, etc. were tried as catalyst support. Of these kieselguhr was found to be the best.

It was further observed that the activity of the V_2O_5 - MoO_3 -kieselguhr catalysts depended on the ratio of V_2O_5/MoO_3 , the optimum being 1 to 2.3. The optimum total oxide ($V_2O_5 + MoO_3 + Co_2O_3$) of the kieselguhr supported catalysts was found to be 22%.

Various oxides like Co_2O_3 , WO_3 , UO_3 , ZrO_2 , TiO_2 , etc. were incorporated with V_2O_5 - MoO_3 -kieselguhr catalyst to investigate their promoting activity. Co_2O_3 was found to be the best promoter. Addition of 2% cobalt oxide to vanadium pentoxide-molybdenum trioxide-kieselguhr catalyst was almost totally ineffective, but the catalyst with nearly 3% of cobalt oxide (on the basis of the total weight of the supported catalyst) was very active. With this catalyst (9) (V_2O_5 - MoO_3 - Co_2O_3 -kieselguhr) though the maximum conversion was 57%, as in the case of unpromoted catalyst, the maximum S. T. Y. was considerably higher, the conversion being almost constant for a wide range of space velocity (2500 to 11000 l./h./l.). Further additions of cobalt oxide reduced the activity.

Various methods of preparation of V_2O_5 - MoO_3 -kieselguhr were adopted to find out the effect of method of preparation on the catalytic activity. It was observed that the catalyst prepared by thermal decomposition of oxalate salts was the most active. With this catalyst a maximum conversion of 57% was obtained. The catalyst prepared by this method was also found to retain its activity for a longer time.

Bhattacharyya and Venkataraman⁸ measured the surface area of different catalyst

samples by B. E. T. method to find out a definite relation between catalytic activity and surface area; but no such correlation was achieved (Table I).

TABLE I
Surface area and catalytic activity.

Catalyst No. or support.	Surface area (m ² /g.).	Max.S.T.Y. (maleic acid), (g./h./l.).	
1 (V ₂ O ₅)	23.51	79.7	
2 (MoO ₃)	11.38	2.8	
4 (V ₂ O ₅ -MoO ₃)	16.09	220.1	Influence of catalyst composition.
9 (V ₂ O ₅ -MoO ₃ -Co ₃ O ₄)	10.72	229.1	
36 (6.8% oxides)	20.41	65.5	
37 (12.8% oxides)	12.54	107.6	Influence of catalyst concentration
38 (22.6% oxides)	11.42	226.0	
9 (36.9% oxides)	10.72	229.1	
39 (46.7% oxides)	10.42	225.9	
40 (53.8% oxides)	10.24	222.9	
35 (ammonium salt method)	10.34	145.6	Influence of method of preparation
4 (oxalic acid method)	16.09	220.1	
9 (kieselguhr)	10.72	229.1	
26 (pumice)	3.16	159.2	
27 (kaolin)	11.57	209.7	Influence of nature of support
28 (silica gel)	320.3	Nil	
33 (ignited kieselguhr)	8.38	197.0	
34 (B.D.H. kieselguhr)	..	149.7	
Purified Indian kieselguhr	30.44	..	
Purified (ignited, 400 for 4 h.)	23.97	..	
B.D.H. kieselguhr (flux calcined)	1.44	..	Surface area data on supports
B.D.H. pumice, purified	1.31	..	
Silica gel	383.10	..	

A calculation of the extent of chemisorption of oxygen on these catalysts in relation to surface areas showed that only 0.8% of surface was active in catalyst (1), assuming monolayer chemisorption. The respective values in catalysts (4) and (9) were 9.7% and 13.4%. When compared on the basis of adsorption per unit area of the surface, the amounts of oxygen adsorbed were uniformly higher in the case of more active catalysts.

The differential heats of adsorption, Q , were calculated according to the equation:

$$\log p_1 - \log p_2 = \frac{Q}{4.58} \left(\frac{1}{T_1} - \frac{1}{T_2} \right)$$

where p_1 and p_2 were the pressures required to give the same amount of adsorption at temperatures T_1 and T_2 respectively. In the temperature interval of the declining isobar (500-540°), there was a definite indication of the existence of activated adsorption. The differential heat of adsorption on 6.5 g. of catalyst (4) was found to be 36,840 cal./mole at 1.3 c.c. (S.T.P.) adsorption and 12,740 cal./mole at 1.8 c.c. adsorption. For the more

active catalyst (9) the corresponding values were 34,340 cal./mole and 14,870 cal./mole. Taylor *et al.*⁹ reported similar results for the adsorption of hydrogen on platinum catalysts.

The value of activation energy, E , according to the equation

$$\log t_1 - \log t_2 = \frac{E}{4.58} \left(\frac{1}{T_1} - \frac{1}{T_2} \right)$$

where t_1 and t_2 are the time periods needed to complete adsorption of a specified amount of gas at temperatures T_1 and T_2 respectively, was constant for catalyst (9) at approximately 41 kcal./mole for adsorption of 0.55-1.10 c.c. (S.T.P.) of oxygen at 480-500°, and was less than the 51 kcal./mole required for adsorption of 1.10 c.c. of oxygen by the less active catalyst (4) in the same temperature range. In the latter case the value of E decreased, however, with the extent of adsorption and was only 37 kcal./mole at 0.65 c.c. adsorption: it was also greatly dependent on the temperature range studied, being nearly 65 kcal./mole at 420-60° and 32 kcal./mole at 480-80° for 0.65 c.c. adsorption. The value of 46 kcal./mole at 480-500° for 1.0 c.c. adsorption on catalyst (4) and the value of 41 kcal./mole for catalyst (9) compared well with the value of 45 kcal./mole observed by Cameron *et al.*¹⁰ who carried out a study of the exchange of isotopic oxygen between vanadium pentoxide and oxygen. Bhattacharyya *et al.*² concluded from their investigations that the high values for activation energy suggested that the process involved either the dissociation of oxygen molecules on the surface of the solid or the loosening of the vanadium-oxygen bonds in vanadium pentoxide.

It has been established quite recently by a number of workers that principal overall reactions can be represented by the following scheme:

The reaction step (I) is supposed to proceed through several consecutive reactions as given below:

Hammar *et al.*¹¹ from their studies on the kinetics of the oxidation of benzene with various catalysts observed that the ratio $k_2/k_1 \cdot k_3$ was near about 0.25. They calculated the activation energies of the three reactions and found them to be lying within a range of 28-4 k-cal./mole. Holsen¹² put forward a general rate equation as follows:

$$\frac{[\text{MA}]}{\Theta_0} = \frac{k_1}{k_3 - (k_2 - k_1)} \times \left(e^{-(k_1 - k_2)t} - e^{-k_3 t} \right)$$

where k_1 = first order rate constant for reaction (I)

k_2 = " " " " " " (II)

k_3 = " " " " " " (III)

Θ_0 = initial benzene concentration

[MA] = concentration of maleic acid.

TABLE II (contd.)

No.	Catalyst.	Space velocity (c.c/hr./c.c.)	Molar air/xylene ratio.	Temp.		Conversion% (anhydride)		Selectivity	Space-time yield (g./hr./l.)
				Bath.	Bed.	Phthalic	Maleic		
11	V ₂ O ₅ -UO ₂ -kieselguhr (31.1:4.6:100)	4290	220	360	450	30.5	16.4	65.0%	38.6
		7145	367	360	430	36.8	12.5	74.7	47.3
12	V ₂ O ₅ -cerium oxide-kieselguhr (31.1:2.9:100)	4290	222	340	460	8.9	5.5	61.8	10.9
13	V ₂ O ₅ -Co ₂ O ₃ -MoO ₃ -kieselguhr (19.5:1.3:7.7:100)	6190	365	380	450	39.0	14.8	72.5	42.8
		8110	206	370	520	37.8	13.7	73.5	98.5
14	Fused V ₂ O ₅	5740	363	460	465	59.0	9.1	86.7	61.4
		5740	275	460	490	61.7	9.6	86.6	85.6
		5740	685	460	475	56.3	7.9	87.8	31.1
15	Fused V ₂ O ₅ -Co ₂ O ₃	5760	290	460	500	55.2	15.5	78.1	72.2
16	Fused V ₂ O ₅ -K ₂ SO ₄ (100:26)	5760	275	470	510	46.0	9.3	83.2	66.1
17	Fused V ₂ O ₅ -kieselguhr (31:1:100)	5760	285	450	510	39.0	10.4	78.9	53.2
18	Fused V ₂ O ₅ -pumice(162:100)	5760	410	480	500	46.9	9.5	83.5	42.0
19	Fused V ₂ O ₅ -pumice (243:100)	5760	383	480	510	51.8	9.3	84.8	51.4
20	Fused V ₂ O ₅ -silica gel (229:100)	5760	290	480	500	48.4	9.4	83.8	63.5

With catalyst (9) the maximum conversion was only 36.6% at 430°. Catalyst (10) was more degradative than (9), maximum conversion being 31.8% at 440°.

The use of UO₂ with V₂O₅ catalyst resulted in a catalyst which was sensitive to heat. At 450° the catalyst showed a conversion of 30.5% to phthalic anhydride. But beyond this temperature there was a sharp fall.

V₂O₅-CeO₂-kieselguhr catalyst gave a very poor conversion to phthalic anhydride, the maximum value recorded being 8.9% at 460°.

The double promoted catalyst V₂O₅-MoO₃-Co₂O₃-kieselguhr exhibited maximum activity at 450°. At this temperature conversion to phthalic anhydride was 39.0%.

Several fused V₂O₅ catalysts were also studied. Fused V₂O₅ did not show any reaction from 320° to 440°. The reaction slowly started at 450° and the catalyst became very active at 480°. At 490° a conversion of 61.7% to phthalic anhydride was obtained.

Incorporation of cobalt oxide in the V₂O₅ made the fused catalyst quite degradative. The activity of this catalyst at 500° was about 5.6% less than that of the unpromoted catalysts.

Fused V₂O₅-K₂SO₄ catalyst was also found to be active only at 450° or more. The conversion to phthalic anhydride was, however, much less, e.g. at 510° it was only 46.03%.

Of the number of supports like kieselguhr, pumice, silica gel, etc., pumice was found to be the best.

The process yield with V₂O₅-pumice (243:100) was 51.8%, whereas the space-time yield was 84.8 g./hr./litre.

Use of oxygen instead of air for the oxidation did not in any way affect the conversion to either phthalic anhydride or maleic anhydride.

The effects of space velocity, temperature, air/xylene ratio on the yield of phthalic anhydride are shown in Figs. 2-4.

FIG. 2. Influence of space velocity on the conversion to phthalic anhydride.

----- S.T.Y.
 ————— % Conversion

FIG. 3. Influence of temperature on the conversion to phthalic anhydride.

----- S.T.Y.
 ————— % Conversion.

FIG. 4. Influence of air/xylene ratio on the conversion to phthalic anhydride.

----- S.T.Y.
 ————— % Conversion

(ii) *p*-Xylene Oxidation.—The chief product of oxidation of *p*-xylene is terephthalic acid, which is extensively used for making synthetic fibres like 'Terylene', and 'Dacron'. The following catalysts were studied for the oxidation of *p*-xylene:

- (1) V_2O_5 —kieselguhr
- (2) V_2O_5 - MoO_3 —kieselguhr
- (3) V_2O_5 - MoO_3 - Co_2O_3 —kieselguhr
- (4) $Sn(VO_3)_4$
- (5) $AgVO_3$
- (6) Fused V_2O_5

Catalyst (1) was sufficiently active at 480° , the conversion to *p*-toluic acid was only 1.0% and to terephthalic acid 0.6%, whereas 21.0% of *p*-xylene passed was converted into maleic anhydride. Temperature increase only augmented the formation of maleic anhydride and *p*-tolualdehyde.

The two promoted catalysts, V_2O_5 - MoO_3 -kieselguhr and V_2O_5 - MoO_3 - Co_2O_3 -kieselguhr, showed a behaviour analogous to the unpromoted catalyst.

In the case of tin vanadate and silver vanadate catalysts, the overall activity of the catalysts was very poor.

The fused V_2O_5 increased the conversion to maleic anhydride, *p*-tolualdehyde, and quinone to an appreciable extent, though the yields of terephthalic acid and *p*-toluic acid did not increase much. For example, at 540° a conversion of 1.1% of *p*-xylene to terephthalic acid, 2.1% to *p*-toluic acid, and 32.3% to maleic anhydride was received at a space-velocity of 5765 c.c./hr./c.c. The vapour phase catalytic oxidation process, which produces such high yields of phthalic anhydride in the case of *o*-xylene oxidation, does not seem to be feasible for the production of terephthalic acid from *p*-xylene.

(iii) *m*-Xylene Oxidation.—The data available on the oxidation of *m*-xylene are extremely meagre. In both the patented and published literatures, mention is made only of laboratory synthesis of isophthalic acid using some of the common oxidising agents, such as $KMnO_4$, $K_2Cr_2O_7$, etc.

The following catalysts were used for the study of oxidation of *m*-xylene:

- (1) V_2O_5 (31.1: 100)
- (2) V_2O_5 - MoO_3 - Co_2O_3 -kieselguhr (19.2:7.7:1.3:100)
- (3) Fused V_2O_5

In the reaction products isophthalic acid, *m*-tolualdehyde, and maleic anhydride were found to be present. No *m*-toluic acid could be detected.

Using catalyst (1) 1.1% conversion to isophthalic acid and 21.3% to maleic anhydride were obtained. With catalyst (2) the conversion to maleic anhydride was greater (22.3%), but the oxidation of other products, i.e., aldehyde, quinone, and isophthalic acid, was of the same order as obtained with unpromoted V_2O_5 -kieselguhr catalyst.

Experiments conducted with fused V_2O_5 catalyst showed that this catalyst gave appreciably higher conversion to aldehyde than the kieselguhr-supported unfused catalysts, reported above. The yields of other products were practically the same. At 550° , the fused V_2O_5 -kieselguhr catalyst gave a conversion of 8.3% to tolualdehyde and 18.2% to maleic anhydride.

Mixed Xylenes.—The oxidation of mixed xylenes gave mainly aldehydes and maleic anhydride. About 18-20% of the xylenes passed were converted to maleic anhydride, whereas the total conversion to the water soluble acids was 22-25%.

(b) Oxidation of Xylenes in the Fluidized Bed

Bhattacharyya and Krishnamurthy¹⁶ employed the fluidized bed of various catalysts for the same reaction and recorded some interesting results. Moreover, during the oxidation of the three xylenes, considerable amount of heat was liberated. Anticipating that these reactions, if carried out under practically isothermal conditions, might lead to improved yield and higher selectivity, they studied these reactions in fluidized bed with various vanadium oxide catalysts.

The vapour phase oxidation of *o*-xylene was studied in the fluidized bed with unfused and fused V_2O_5 catalysts, supported on various proportions of kieselguhr, and also with unfused promoted catalysts under a wide range of temperature, air/xylene ratio, space velocity,

volume of the catalyst, and concentration of CO_2 in the feed. The products obtained using fused catalysts were mainly phthalic anhydride, *o*-tolualdehyde, carbon dioxide, and traces of quinone whilst in the case of static bed, maleic anhydride was present instead of *o*-tolualdehyde. In the case of unfused catalyst in fluidized bed all the above products were found. Fused vanadium pentoxide afforded maximum yield of phthalic anhydride with high selectivity. Under the optimum condition (490° , air/xylene ratio=95.1; space velocity=10,030; volume of the catalyst=17.3 c.c. $\approx$ 20g.) the conversion to phthalic anhydride was 67.8% and that to *o*-tolualdehyde was 3.56%, leading to a selectivity of 95%. One interesting feature with fused vanadium pentoxide catalyst in the oxidation of *o*-xylene under fluidized condition was that the yield of phthalic anhydride increased (with increase in concentration of xylene) when the air/xylene ratio was decreased from 2,230 to 102.5 and again fell down when the air/xylene ratio was further decreased to 53.9. Aldehyde yield fell down considerably when the air/xylene ratio was reduced. This effect was the reverse of that observed previously in the static bed.

Similar studies were made with other catalysts and the result obtained thereby will be reported shortly.

In the case of oxidation of *p*-xylene, under the best condition and with fused V_2O_5 catalyst (465° , air/xylene ratio=365, space velocity=9,550), the conversions to various products are: terephthalaldehydic acid=3.12%; terephthalaldehyde=19.32%; *p*-toluic acid=2.05%; *p*-tolualdehyde=19.91%; maleic anhydride=20.17%; quinone=5.18%. In the static bed terephthalic acid was present, whilst terephthalaldehyde and terephthalaldehydic acid were absent. Under optimum conditions (540° ; air/xylene ratio=121.5; space velocity = 9,300), and using the same catalyst for infuidized condition for oxidation of *m*-xylene, the following product distribution was obtained: Maleic anhydride=32.68%; *m*-tolualdehyde=10.82%; quinone=0.51%. In the static bed, in addition to the above products, isophthalic acid was present in traces.

The effects of space velocity, temperature, and air/xylene ratio on the oxidation of *o*-xylene, using fused V_2O_5 catalyst, both in the fixed and fluidized catalyst beds, are represented in Figures 2-4.

Very recently much attention has been focussed on the mechanism of this oxidation reaction and also on the role of the catalyst.

Simard *et al.*¹⁷ have studied the kinetics of *o*-xylene oxidation at conversions below 25 % over a SiC-supported V_2O_5 catalyst. They have suggested the following scheme of the reaction.

Reaction (I) was found to be first order with respect to *o*-xylene and *o*-tolualdehyde, whereas all other reactions were of zero order.

All the reactions showed a square root dependence on oxygen pressure. Hence it has been suggested that the uptake of oxygen is the rate controlling step.

Simard *et al.*¹⁷ investigated the surface composition of vanadium pentoxide catalyst during the oxidation of *o*-xylene under normal operating conditions and concluded that the catalyst consisted of a mixture of V_2O_5 , $V_2O_{4.34}$, V_2O_4 (and also V_2O_3 under certain conditions). Of these four different oxides, the first two were supposed to act as catalyst components.

Bhattacharyya and Gulati carried out the surface area measurement of various oxidation catalysts but did not find any correlation between the catalytic activity and the specific surface.

To ascertain the changes occurring in the catalyst during the reaction, the kinetics of oxygen adsorption was also studied over spent catalyst samples. A significant increase in the rate and amount of oxygen adsorption was observed in the case of spent catalysts. The results obtained by them have been discussed elaborately in a previous publication².

This kinetic study indicated that, during the oxidation reaction, the catalyst partly decomposed to a lower oxide; this was oxidised rapidly to the original oxide as soon as oxygen was introduced into the system at 520°. During the reaction, when air was present along with the *o*-xylene vapors, reoxidation of the catalyst occurred simultaneously with its reduction, setting up an equilibrium. Presumably, this equilibrium had almost been established when the *o*-xylene oxidation step was discontinued and the catalyst was flushed with nitrogen.

Even without passing the mixture of air and xylene, the fused vanadium pentoxide catalyst lost part of its chemically bound oxygen on being degassed at 520° and was reoxidised as soon as oxygen pressure in the system was increased. This indicated the mobility of oxygen in the vanadium pentoxide lattice at this temperature. In the presence of *o*-xylene, oxygen exchange between the gas phase and bulk phase was greatly facilitated because of the continuous reduction of the solid by the hydrocarbon.

Oxidation of Crotonaldehyde in the Fixed Bed

The catalytic oxidation of crotonaldehyde to maleic acid has not been investigated in any great detail. The only published work is that due to Faith and Schaible¹⁸. Using air/aldehyde ratio of about 300, the maximum conversion to maleic acid was reported as 42.2%, obtained with vanadium pentoxide deposited on aluminium granules. Much higher values for the conversion to maleic acid have been claimed in the patent literature. A systematic study of the vapour phase oxidation on crotonaldehyde to maleic acid in its manifold aspects was therefore undertaken by Bhattacharyya and his coworkers¹⁹. Only the salient features of their observations and the results of their recent investigations of fluidized bed synthesis have been discussed here.

Numerous catalysts consisting of the oxides of vanadium, molybdenum, tungsten, uranium and cobalt, supported on purified kieselguhr, were prepared by the familiar oxalic acid method, described in the discussion on the studies of oxidation of benzene. The vanadates of Ag, Sn, Bi, and Pb were obtained by the double decomposition between the soluble salts of the metals and alkali metavanadate. Each catalyst was subjected to a

mixture of crotonaldehyde and air/crotonaldehyde ratio=160 to 180, for at least 4 hours at 250-300° before its efficiency for the oxidation was studied.

Various V_2O_5 -kieselguhr catalysts, promoted by UO_3 , Co_2O_3 , MoO_3 , WO_3 and vanadates of Ag, Pb, Bi, and Sn, were tested for their catalytic activity.

The oxidation of crotonaldehyde to maleic acid could evidently be carried out fairly efficiently with a catalyst consisting of the oxides of vanadium and molybdenum, supported on purified Indian kieselguhr. ($V_2O_5:MoO_3$: Kg=38.9:686:100) or with a tin vanadate catalyst obtained by the double decomposition between aqueous solutions of stannous chloride and ammonium metavanadate.

At a space-velocity of about 12,000 l/hr./g., a process conversion of about 77% maleic acid was obtained with a catalyst consisting of the oxides of V and Mo supported on kieselguhr (Temp: 310° & air/aldehyde=150). Under similar conditions tin vanadate catalyst registered a process conversion of about 60% acid at the lower temperature of 230°.

From the studies of material balance it was concluded that besides the oxidation of crotonaldehyde to maleic acid and CO_2 , crotonaldehyde was found to undergo decomposition and polymerisation losses appreciably.

The general behaviour of the catalysts with respect to various factors were found to be more or less similar in case of the oxidation of benzene and crotonaldehyde. It was surprising that the conversions to maleic acid obtained in the oxidation of crotonaldehyde were not as high as would be expected. This is particularly so in view of the fact that the molecule is expected to lend itself to oxidation with greater ease owing to the presence of easily oxidisable groups in it.

The effects of space velocity, temperature and air/aldehyde ratio on the conversion to and S.T.Y. of maleic acid using V_2O_5 - MoO_3 -kieselguhr, the best catalyst, are shown in Figs. 5-7.

Oxidation of Crotonaldehyde in Fluidized Catalyst Bed

Anticipating that the isothermal condition in a fluidized bed would lead to improved yield of maleic acid, Bhattacharyya and Kar²⁰ recently employed the fluidized catalyst bed for the oxidation of crotonaldehyde. They obtained very promising results and an extensive study in this line is still being pursued. Some of their encouraging observations are discussed below.

V_2O_5 - MoO_3 (85:15), supported on pumice (28% total oxide), has been found to be the best catalyst for the reaction. Using this catalyst the conversions of crotonaldehyde to maleic acid at 325°, space velocity of 9022 c.c./hr./c.c. of catalyst and air/aldehyde ratios of 286, 444.1 and 700 were 66.87, 71.32, and 85.86% respectively. With further increase of air/aldehyde ratio, the actual conversion of crotonaldehyde to maleic acid increased, but space-time yield decreased. Carbon dioxide was the only byproduct of the reaction.

The conversions achieved by varying temperature, catalyst volume, air/aldehyde ratio, and space velocity, one at a time, are shown in Figs. 5-7.

Oxidation of Picoline to Nicotinic Acid in the Fluidized Bed

Catalytic oxidation of β -picoline to nicotinic acid, a valuable precursor of important medicines, either in the liquid phase or in vapour phase, has not been well studied and

FIG. 5. Influence of space velocity on the conversion to maleic acid.

Δ : S.T.T. $\circ$: % Conversion.

FIG. 6. Influence of temperature on the conversion to maleic acid.

FIG. 7. Influence of air/aldehyde ratio on the conversion to maleic acid.

Δ : S.T.Y. O : % Conversion.

most of the informations have been guarded in patent literature. Moreover, the production of nicotinic acid from β -picoline in the fluidized catalyst bed is exclusively unexplored. Its vapour phase oxidation to nicotinic acid was carried out by Bhattacharyya and Kar²⁰ in a fluidized catalyst bed of fused and unfused vanadium pentoxide. The influence of temperature, air/picoline ratio, and space velocity on the conversion of picoline to nicotinic acid was exhaustively studied. With the unfused V_2O_5 : pumice (51.84: 100) catalyst the maximum yield of nicotinic acid was 16.65% (of theoretical) with 60 c.c. of catalyst under the optimum conditions of a temperature of 375°, air/picoline ratio of 225 and at a space velocity of 2395 c.c./hr./c.c. of catalyst. The percentage conversion of nicotinic acid on the basis of total picoline oxidised was 63.08%.

Using fused V_2O_5 on pumice (70:30) a maximum conversion of 24.37% (of theoretical) of β -picoline to nicotinic acid was achieved with 20 c.c. of catalyst at 490°, air/picoline ratio of 225, and at a space velocity of 5004 c.c./hr./c.c. of catalyst. The percentage conversion of nicotinic acid on the basis of total picoline oxidised was 51.42.

Further work in this line is in progress.

Conclusion

It has not been possible to discuss the oxidation of organic compounds in its full length within this short compass. The authors have concentrated mainly on the range of their work in this field. Besides the oxidation reactions reviewed here, oxidation of naphthalene, anthracene, acetylene, etc. has also drawn the interest of the scientists and technologists.

It has been quite clear that the application of fluidized catalyst technique, by facilitating uniform temperature distribution throughout the catalyst bed and by increasing the

available catalyst surface, has brought about considerable improvements in all the oxidation processes.

But it must be pointed out that this technique of fluidization favours only the reactions having high equilibrium constants; because otherwise, the equilibrium conversions are adversely affected due to the back-mixing of the products in the catalyst bed.

The studies on the physico-chemical properties of the important oxidation catalysts, by employing the techniques of X-ray diffraction, differential thermal analysis, semi-conductivity measurements, adsorption measurements, etc. have recently evoked much scientific interest and have opened a new avenue for research. These investigations will surely evince the fundamental mechanism of contact catalysis as a whole, in all its intricacies and ramifications and thus will help the development of better catalysts.

Nomenclature

Space velocity (S.V.) in c.c./hr./c.c. represents volume in c.c. of the inlet reaction mixture at N.T.P. flowing per hour per c.c. of the catalyst.

Contact time (C.T.) in seconds.—Volume of the catalyst in c.c./volume of the inlet gas mixture at the bed temperature and at the reaction pressure flowing per second.

Selectivity.—This is given by the relationship:

$\% \text{ Conversion of a reactant to the desired product} \times 100 / \text{total conversion of the reactant.}$

Space-time yield (S.T.Y.) in c.c./hr./c.c.—Volume at N.T.P. of the product produced per hour per volume of the catalyst space.

REFERENCES

1. McBee *et al.*, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1945, **37**, 432.
2. Bhattacharyya *et al.*, Proc. of the Symp. on Contact Catalysis, National Inst. of Sciences of India, 1959, No. 12, pp. 147, 171.
3. Twigg, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1946, **42**, 284.
4. Murray, *Austral. J. Res.*, 1950, **3A**, 433.
5. Andrianova and Todes, *J. Phys. Chem. U.S.S.R.*, 1960, **30**, 522.
6. Orzechowski and MacCormack, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1954, **32**, 388, 415, 432, 443.
7. Weiss and Downs, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1920, **12**, 228; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **45**, 1003, 2341.
8. Bhattacharyya and Venkataraman, *J. Appl. Chem.*, 1958, **8**, 728.
9. Taylor *et al.*, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, **34**, 799.
10. Cameron *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1953, **57**, 239.
11. Hammar *et al.*, *Svenska kem. Tidskr.*, 1952, **64**, 165.
12. Emmet, 'Catalysis', Vol. VII, Reinhold Publishing Corp., N.Y., 1960, p. 192.
13. Thampy *et al.*, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1959, **18B**, 147.
14. Park and Allard, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1939, **31**, 1162.
15. Bhattacharyya *et al.*, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1958, **50**, 1719.
16. Bhattacharyya and Krishnamurthy, *Cur. Sci.*, 1959, **28**, 363.
17. Simard *et al.*, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1955, **47**, 1424.
18. Faith and Schaible, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **60**, 52.
19. Bhattacharyya and his co-workers, *J. Appl. Chem.*, 1958, **8**, 737.
20. Bhattacharyya and Kar, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1960, **19B**, 78.